

Interview Script for the Head of Technology and her/his acting in business

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This document is a supplementary material of the paper “Analyzing the BizDev Interface in an Enterprise Context: A Case of Developers Acting in Business” by Caique G. Moreira, Breno B. N. de França, and Tayana U. Conte. Here, we provide the interview script applied to the Head of Technology.

Warm Up:

- For how long have you been in the company?
- What is your current Job Position?

Acting in Business:

- [Inform the interviewee that her/his act in business will be the focus of the interview]
- What was your motivation for acting in business? What was the company's influence in it? What was your leader's influence in it?
- How was the process of proposing new projects? How was the communication with the business sector during this process? How easy was for you to convince the business sector of the importance of your proposed projects?
- How do you evaluate the results of your proposed projects?
- What's your perception of other projects idealized by the IT sector, regarding new features inside ProductP?
 - Were there such projects?
 - Were they successful?
 - Do you believe something could have been done differently?